

Extraction Chromatographic Studies of Cerium(IV) with Carboxylic Acid (n-Capric Acid) and its Separation from Rare Earth Elements

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Cerium(IV) was extracted at pH 4.75 – 6.0 from ammonium acetate-acetic acid buffer on silica gel column impregnated with n-capric acid (a high molecular weight carboxylic acid). It was separated from bivalent Mg, Mn, Co, Ni, Zn and Cd in binary mixture at pH 5.1 as they could not form acetate complex. Cerium(IV) was separated by process of selective elution from elements like Fe^{III}, Zr^{IV}, Pd^{II}, La^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III}, Gd^{III}, Dy^{III}, Hg^{II}, Pb^{II}, Th^{IV} and U^{VI} by exploiting differences in stability of acetate complexes. Cerium(IV) was separated from multicomponent mixture containing Zn^{II}, Zr^{IV}, Pb^{II}, Th^{IV}, U^{VI} and rare earth elements by a process of selective sorption and selective elution. The proposed method is simple, rapid and selective.

There are several reports in the literature on the extraction of metals with high molecular weight carboxylic acids^{1,2}. Cerium(IV) has been separated from rare earth elements by solvent extraction with Versatic 9³ and the extraction of cerium(III) with Versatic 911 by solvent extraction has been reported⁴. The extraction chromatographic behaviour of cerium(IV) on a silica gel column impregnated with carboxylic acid (SRS 100) has also been reported⁵ but work on extraction of cerium(IV) with organic liquid cation exchanger (n-capric acid) by this technique is lacking. Therefore this paper presents the systematic study on extraction chromatographic behaviour of cerium(IV) on silica gel column impregnated with n-capric acid.

Results and Discussion

The systematic studies on extraction chromatography of cerium(IV) at pH 4–6 from acetate buffer (acetic acid and ammonium acetate) showed that cerium was quantitatively extracted at pH 4.75–6.0. Flow rate upto 2.5 ml min⁻¹ during extraction showed the complete retention of cerium(IV) in the column. Common anions like nitrate, sulphate and halides did not interfere in the extraction. Hydrochloric, sulphuric, nitric, mixed acid (hydrochloric and sulphuric), ammonium nitrate and demineralised water were tested as the eluents. The results, using a column (0.8 × 5.5 cm) containing 210.8 µg Ce^{IV} with a flow rate of the eluents 1 ml min⁻¹, showed that the stripping of Ce^{IV} was complete with 1 M H₂SO₄, 3.5 M HCl, 1 M HNO₃ and a mixture of HCl and H₂SO₄ as well each of 1 M in the ratio 1 : 1 (v/v). There was no elution with ammonium nitrate (≤ 4 M) and with demineralised water. 1 M H₂SO₄ was used as eluent in subsequent experiments.

Breakthrough capacity: Breakthrough capacity, i.e. the number of milliequivalent of ions which can be retained without any leakage being observed with

respect to cerium in capric acid coated on silica gel, was determined at pH 5.0 and 5.75. The leakage of cerium was observed to start at pH 5.0 and 5.75 after passing 32 and 44 ml (1.05 mg of Ce per ml) of the effluent respectively. Hence the uptake of cerium increases with increase in pH.

Separation of Ce^{IV} from binary mixtures: It was possible to separate cerium from several elements in binary mixture by exploiting the difference in pH at which they formed complexes. At pH 5.1, bivalent Mg, Mn, Co, Ni, Zn and Cd were not extracted along with Ce^{IV}, i.e. they passed through the column but cerium was extracted. Later, cerium was stripped with H₂SO₄ (10 ml; 1 M). A mixture containing Fe^{III} and Ce^{IV} was passed through the column at pH 3—cerium passed through the column with the mobile phase while the extracted iron was eluted with HCl (10 ml; 0.2 M). The separation of Ce^{IV} from binary mixtures containing Y^{III}, Zr^{IV}, Pd^{II}, La^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III}, Gd^{III}, Dy^{III}, Hg^{II}, Pb^{II} or U^{VI} was achieved by passing the mixture at pH 5.1 when each of the foreign ions along with Ce^{IV} were exchanged and extracted. Th^{IV} along with Ce^{IV} were extracted at pH 4.8. Except Zr, in all cases the diverse ion was eluted first with specific eluents, like Y, La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd or Dy were stripped with HNO₃ (0.025 M), Pd with HCl (0.25 M), Hg with HNO₃ (0.02 M), Pb with HNO₃ (0.002 M), Th with HNO₃ (0.2 M) and U with HNO₃ (0.01 M), later Ce was stripped with H₂SO₄ (1 M). In case of the mixture of cerium and zirconium, Ce was eluted first with H₂SO₄ (1 M) followed by Zr with HNO₃ (4 M). After separation, cerium was determined spectrophotometrically⁶ while the foreign ions were estimated complexometrically⁷. The results of binary separations are given in Table 1.

Separation of cerium(IV) from synthetic mixtures:

Separation of Ce^{IV}, Th^{IV} and Zr^{IV}: Synthetic mixture containing Ce, Th and Zr in different

TABLE 1—SEPARATION OF Ce^{IV} FROM BINARY MIXTURES*

Ce taken = 210.8 μg, column = 0.8 × 5.5 cm, flow rate = 1 ml min⁻¹

Metal ion	Metal ion added (mg)	Metal ion recovered (mg)	Recovery of Ce (μg)
Mg ^{II}	0.96	0.95	208.6
Mn ^{II}	1.40	1.39	207.9
Fe ^{III} ^a	1.31	1.32	209.3
Co ^{II}	1.08	1.06	207.9
Ni ^{II}	1.55	1.53	208.6
Zn ^{II}	3.06	3.0	208.6
Cd ^{II}	2.25	2.21	207.2
Hg ^{II}	1.68	1.63	209.3
Pd ^{II}	2.13	2.07	207.2
Y ^{III}	1.22	1.21	209.3
La ^{III}	2.78	2.69	208.6
Pr ^{III}	2.52	2.49	208.6
Nd ^{III}	2.52	2.47	208.6
Sm ^{III}	2.67	2.64	209.3
Dy ^{III}	2.44	2.42	208.6
Gd ^{III}	2.01	1.98	208.6
Pb ^{II} ^o	2.46	2.40	229.9
Zr ^{IV}	1.73	1.68	203.7
Th ^{IV} ^b	2.62	2.60	209.3
U ^{VI}	3.35	3.30	208.6

*pH values = 5.1, ^a3.0, ^b4.8. ^oCe taken = 232 μg as Ce(NO₃)₄.

proportion was passed through the column at pH 4.8; the three together were extracted. Th was stripped with HNO₃ (0.2 M) then Ce with H₂SO₄ (1 M) followed by Zr with HNO₃ (4 M).

Separation of Ce^{IV}, Th^{IV} and U^{VI}: A mixture of Ce, Th and U was passed through the column at pH 4.8. U was first eluted with HNO₃ (0.01 M) followed by Th with HNO₃ (0.2 M) and Ce with H₂SO₄ (1 M).

Separation of Ce^{IV}, Pb^{II} and Dy^{III}: These three elements were separated from each other by passing the mixture at pH 5.1. Pb was first stripped with HNO₃ (0.002 M) then Dy with HNO₃ (0.025 M) followed by Ce with H₂SO₄ (1 M).

Separation of Ce^{IV}, Sm^{III} and Ni^{II}: The separation of these elements was accomplished at pH 5.1. Ni was passed through the column with the mobile phase while Sm and Ce were extracted. Sm was stripped from the column with HNO₃ (0.025 M) followed by Ce with H₂SO₄ (1 M).

Separation of Ce^{IV}, Th^{IV}, Pb^{II} and Gd^{III}: Synthetic mixture containing these elements in different proportion was passed through the column at pH 4.8, where all elements were extracted. Lead was first stripped with HNO₃ (0.002 M) then Gd with HNO₃ (0.025 M) followed by Th with HNO₃ (0.2 M) and finally Ce with H₂SO₄ (1 M).

Separation of Ce^{IV}, Th^{IV}, U^{VI} and Zr^{IV}: A mixture containing these elements in different proportions, was passed through the column at pH 4.8 where all the elements were extracted. U was first eluted with HNO₃ (0.01 M) then Th with HNO₃ (0.02 M) followed by Ce with H₂SO₄ (1 M) and Zr with HNO₃ (4 M). The results are given in Table 2.

TABLE—2 SEPARATION OF Ce^{IV} FROM SYNTHETIC MIXTURES*

Column = 0.8 × 5.5 cm, flow rate = 1 ml min⁻¹

Cations	Weight added (μg)	Weight recovery (μg)	Recovery %	Eluent (vol, ml)
Th ^{IV}	2 622	2 645	100.9	0.2 M HNO ₃ (30)
Ce ^{IV}	210.8	207.2	98.3	1 M H ₂ SO ₄ (10)
Zr ^{IV}	1 733	1 687	97.3	4 M HNO ₃ (30)
U ^{VI}	3 356	3 308	98.6	0.01 M HNO ₃ (25)
Th ^{IV}	2 622	2 598	99.1	0.2 M HNO ₃ (30)
Ce ^{IV}	210.8	208.6	99.0	1 M H ₂ SO ₄ (10)
Pb ^{II}	2 465	2 424	98.3	0.002 M HNO ₃ (25)
Dy ^{III}	2 437	2 453	100.6	0.025 M HNO ₃ (12.5)
Ce ^{IV}	232	230.6	99.4	1 M H ₂ SO ₄ (10)
Ni ^{II}	1 550	1 538	99.2	—
Sm ^{III}	2 676	2 692	100.6	0.025 M HNO ₃ (12.5)
Ce ^{IV}	210.8	211.4	100.3	1 M H ₂ SO ₄ (10)
Pb ^{II}	2 465	2 444	99.1	0.002 M HNO ₃ (25)
Gd ^{III}	2 013	1 997	99.2	0.025 M HNO ₃ (12.5)
Th ^{IV}	2 622	2 645	100.9	0.2 M HNO ₃ (30)
Ce ^{IV}	232	232.7	100.9	1 M H ₂ SO ₄ (10)
U ^{VI}	3 356	3 308	98.6	0.01 M HNO ₃ (25)
Th ^{IV}	2 622	2 598	99.1	0.2 M HNO ₃ (30)
Ce ^{IV}	210.8	207.2	98.3	1 M H ₂ SO ₄ (10)
Zr ^{IV}	1 733	1 678	96.8	4 M HNO ₃ (30)
Mn ^{II}	1 406	1 395	99.2	—
U ^{VI}	3 356	3 332	99.3	0.01 M HNO ₃ (25)
Th ^{IV}	2 622	2 622	100.0	0.2 M HNO ₃ (30)
Ce ^{IV}	210.8	208.6	99.0	1 M H ₂ SO ₄ (10)

Separation of Ce^{IV} from other rare earth elements: Ce^{IV} was separated from other rare earth elements by passing a mixture through the column at pH 5 where all the elements were extracted. The diverse lanthanides were stripped from the column with HNO₃ (0.025 M) followed by Ce with H₂SO₄ (1 M). The results of separations are given in Table 3.

TABLE - 3 SEPARATION OF Ce^{IV} FROM SYNTHETIC MIXTURES CONTAINING RARE EARTH ELEMENTS

Cerium(IV) taken = 210.8 μg, column = 0.8 × 5.5 cm, flow rate = 1 ml min⁻¹, pH = 5

Cations	Weight of cerium(IV) taken (μg)	Weight of cerium(IV) recovered (μg)	Recovery of cerium(IV) (%)
Ce ^{IV} + Pr ^{III} + Nd ^{III}	210.8	203.7	96.6
Ce ^{IV} + Sm ^{III} + Gd ^{III}	210.8	204.4	97.0
Ce ^{IV} + Sm ^{III} + Dy ^{III}	210.8	205.1	97.3
Ce ^{IV} + La ^{III} + Pr ^{III} + Nd ^{III}	210.8	200.2	95.0
Ce ^{IV} + La ^{III} + Gd ^{III} + Dy ^{III}	210.8	200.9	95.3

The proposed method is simple, rapid, selective and permits separation of cerium from its commonly associated elements like Th, Zr, U, Pb and rare earths. The separation of cerium from these elements is very important as they are associated with cerium in minerals and ores. The overall time required for extraction and separation does not exceed 2.5 h.

Experimental

An Elico LI-120 pH meter provided with glass and saturated calomel electrodes, a ECIL GS 5700 A spectrophotometer, a Dimmerstat 7D-IF hot-

cum-cold bath and the chromatographic column (i.d., 0.8 cm ; bed height, 5.5 cm) of borosil glass with a glass wool plug at the bottom, were used.

Capric acid (C.R., Wako) was distilled thrice and used as liquid cation-exchanger. A stock solution of cerium (5.27 mg ml^{-1}) was prepared by dissolving $2(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (A.R.) in H_2SO_4 (1 M) and standardised complexometrically with EDTA⁷. Ascorbic acid was used for the reduction of Ce^{IV} . Buffer solutions of different pH were prepared from acetic acid (0.2 M) and ammonium acetate (0.2 M). Solution containing $105.4 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of Ce^{IV} was prepared through appropriate dilution.

Preparation of ion-exchange material : Silica gel (60–120 mesh) was rendered hydrophobic by exposing it to the vapours of dimethyldichlorosilane in an atmosphere of nitrogen, then washed with anhydrous methanol and dried at 100° . 1 ml of dimethyldichlorosilane was found adequate for 10 g of silica gel. The silanated silica gel was coated by treatment with a benzene solution of capric acid and the excess benzene was then evaporated. Hydrophobic silica gel (1 g) could take up 0.9 ml of capric acid. A slurry of the coated silica gel in distilled water was prepared by centrifugation (1500 rpm) and the coated gel was packed into the chromatographic column to give a bed height of 5.5 cm. The column was washed with HCl (4 M). Silica gel was preferred as the support because of its porosity and retained a considerable amount of extractant. Each column could be used for at least 25 cycles without the loss of exchange capacity.

The exchange capacity of the exchanger was

determined at different temperatures (viz. 25, 35, 40, 50 and 60°) through equilibration (shaking for 6 h) of H^+ -form of the dry exchanger ($\sim 1 \text{ g}$) with an aqueous solution (50 ml) containing sodium chloride and sodium hydroxide (2.5 M NaCl, 25 ml + $\sim 0.2 \text{ M}$ NaOH, 15 ml + demineralised water 15 ml) and titrating the excess alkali with standard HCl ($\sim 0.22 \text{ M}$). The exchange capacity was found to be $2.09 (\pm 0.03) \text{ meq/g}$ (dry exchange).

General extraction procedure : An aliquot containing Ce^{IV} ($210.8 \mu\text{g}$) was mixed with acetate buffer (10 ml) and adjusted to the desired pH with acetic acid (0.2 M) or ammonium acetate (0.2 M). The solution was passed through the pretreated chromatographic column loaded with n-capric acid coated on silica gel (2 g), at a flow rate of 1 ml min^{-1} . After extraction, cerium was stripped with different mineral acids and salt solutions. Five fractions (2 ml each) were collected and cerium from each fraction was determined spectrophotometrically at 305 nm° .

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